
LEPIDOPTERA DISSECTION REPORT 2025: 01

A REPORT ON THE IDENTIFICATION OF VC55 LEPIDOPTERA BY DISSECTION AND MICRO-PHOTOGRAPHY

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Abstract

This report records the determinations made by microscopic examination of Lepidoptera specimens made by VC55 recorders. Each determination is illustrated by micro-photographs of specimens and temporary slides.

Introduction

This report records the determinations made by microscopic examination of Lepidoptera specimens submitted by VC55 recorders. Most specimens have been set and retained. In addition, each determination is illustrated with microphotographs of the specimens and temporary slides.

In this report, most of the high quality microphotographs have been produced as single images from carefully prepared slides under good illumination, rather than by focus stacking, in order to save time. In most cases, these images provide a clearer view of dissected structures than can be seen directly through the microscope.

It should be noted that the preparation and processing of focus stacked photographs can take several hours of work. While such high quality images have become the standard for the publication of reference material, the authors have adopted a more pragmatic voucher standard for the purposes of this report.

The use of microphotographs has also enabled online collaboration with other experts to confirm identifications. Such assistance is acknowledged in the individual specimen accounts.

The primary sources for identifying Lepidoptera by dissection used in this work are Hall et al. (2021) and Schön (2021). The determination was also checked against the appearance of the imago using Kimber (2021) amongst other sources.

Species Summary

The species included in this report are presented in Table 1.

*Thanks to: Andy Mitchell, Derek Lee, Peter Hall and Guy Meredith for their help with determinations.

Table 1: Species recorded by family.

taxon	Count	gender	FamilyCount
Tortricidae			
Acleris emargana	1	female	
Acleris ferrugana	1	male	
Ancyliis diminutana	1	female	
Cnephasia sp.	1	female	
Dichrorampha alpinana	1	female	
Endothenia marginana	1	male	
Epinotia immundana	1	female	
Epinotia solandriana	1	male	
No ID	2	female	
Notocelia rosaecolana	2	male	
Syndemis musculana	2	male	
Number of records for this family:			14
Geometridae			
Aplocera plagiata	1	female	
Eupithecia dodoneata	1	male	
Eupithecia indigata	2	male	
Eupithecia pulchellatta	1	male	
Number of records for this family:			5
Depressariidae			
Agonopterix heracliana	4	male	
Number of records for this family:			4
Blastobasidae			
Blastobasis vittata	3	male	
Number of records for this family:			3
Coleophoridae			
Coleophora flavipennella	1	female	
Coleophora sp.	1	NULL	
Number of records for this family:			2
Crambidae			
Anania coronata	1	male	
Scoparia ambigualis	1	female	
Number of records for this family:			2
Elachistidae			
Elachista consortella	1	female	
No ID	1	NULL	
Number of records for this family:			2
Autostichidae			
Oegoconia quadripuncta	1	male	
Number of records for this family:			1
Gelechiidae			
Anacampsis blattariella	1	male	
Number of records for this family:			1
Tineidae			
Nemapogon cloacella	1	male	
Number of records for this family:			1

Figure 1: Map of all records by tetrad.

Figure 2: Phenology of all records.

Lepidoptera Records

Specimen PJP20250307-01 *Agonopterix heracliiana*

Label details: record.date: 2025-03-07, site: Melton Mowbray Garden, VC: VC55, grid.ref: SK 7563 1803, recorder.name: Paul Palmer, comments: Agonopterix?, determiner: Pete Leonard, method: Actinic Trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Depressariidae, sub.family: Depressariinae, genus: Agonopterix, taxon: Agonopterix heracliiana, log.number: 32.018, Code: 688, and gender: male.

Figure 3: PJP20250307-01 *Agonopterix heracliiana* specimen images.

Dissection

A tricky dissection, with much detail obscured, but the visible parts strongly suggest this species.

Figure 4: PJP20250307-01 *Agonopterix heracliiana* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PJP20250323-01 *Agonopterix heracliiana*

Label details: record.date: 2025-03-21, site: Rutland NR, VC: VC55, grid.ref: SK 8831 0772, recorder.name: Paul Palmer, comments: Micro, determiner: Pete Leonard, method: Actinic Trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Depressariidae, sub.family: Depressariinae, genus: Agonopterix, taxon: Agonopterix heracliiana, log.number: 32.018, Code: 688, and gender: male.

Figure 5: PJP20250323-01 *Agonopterix heracliiana* specimen images.

Dissection

A good visual match - showing the untwisted and sinuate distal process of the sacculus.

Figure 6: PJP20250323-01 *Agonopterix heracliana* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PJP20250323-02 *Agonopterix heracliana*

Label details: record.date: 2025-03-21, site: Rutland NR, VC: VC55, grid.ref: SK 8831 0772, recorder.name: Paul Palmer, comments: Micro, determiner: Pete Leonard, method: Actinic Trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Depressariidae, sub.family: Depressariinae, genus: Agonopterix, taxon: Agonopterix heracliana, log.number: 32.018, Code: 688, and gender: male.

Figure 7: PJP20250323-02 *Agonopterix heracliana* specimen images.

Dissection

The untwisted and sinuate distal process of the sacculus is just visible, confirming this species.

Figure 8: PJP20250323-02 *Agonopterix heracliana* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PJP20250429-01 *Eupithecia indigata* Ochreous Pug

Label details: record.date: 2025-04-29, site: Melton Mowbray Garden, VC: VC55, grid.ref: SK 7563 1803, recorder.name: Paul Palmer, comments: Eupithecia, determiner: Pete Leonard, method: Actinic Trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Geometridae, sub.family: Larentiinae, genus: Eupithecia, taxon: Eupithecia indigata, log.number: 70.171, Code: 1844, vernacular: Ochreous Pug, and gender: male.

Figure 9: PJP20250429-01 *Eupithecia indigata* Ochreous Pug specimen images.

Dissection

Good visual match on all parts.

Figure 10: PJP20250429-01 *Eupithecia indigata* Ochreous Pug temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PJP20250429-02 *Eupithecia pulchellatta* Foxglove Pug

Label details: record.date: 2025-04-29, site: Melton Mowbray Garden, VC: VC55, grid.ref: SK 7563 1803, recorder.name: Paul Palmer, comments: Eupithecia, determiner: Pete Leonard, method: Actinic Trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Geometridae, sub.family: Larentiinae, genus: Eupithecia, taxon: Eupithecia pulchellatta, log.number: 70.151, Code: 1817, vernacular: Foxglove Pug, and gender: male.

Figure 11: PJP20250429-02 *Eupithecia pulchellatta* Foxglove Pug specimen images.

Dissection

The cornuti are as long as the aedeagus and on the imago, there is a notch on the outer margin of the central dark cross band.

Figure 12: PJP20250429-02 *Eupithecia pulchellatta* Foxglove Pug temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PJP20250504-01 *Syndemis musculana*

Label details: record.date: 2025-05-04, site: Melton Mowbray Garden, VC: VC55, grid.ref: SK 7563 1803, recorder.name: Paul Palmer, comments: No Comment, determiner: Pete Leonard, method: Actinic Trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Tortricidae, sub.family: Tortricinae, genus: Syndemis, taxon: Syndemis musculana, log.number: 49.028, Code: 986, and gender: male.

Figure 13: PJP20250504-01 *Syndemis musculana* specimen images.

Dissection

Good visual match.

Figure 14: PJP20250504-01 *Syndemis musculana* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PJP20250504-02 *Syndemis musculana*

Label details: record.date: 2025-05-04, site: Melton Mowbray Garden, VC: VC55, grid.ref: SK 7563 1803, recorder.name: Paul Palmer, comments: Cnephasia, determiner: Pete Leonard, method: Actinic Trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Tortricidae, sub.family: Tortricinae, genus: Syndemis, taxon: Syndemis musculana, log.number: 49.028, Code: 986, and gender: male.

Figure 15: PJP20250504-02 *Syndemis musculana* specimen images.

Dissection

Very good visual match.

Figure 16: PJP20250504-02 *Syndemis musculana* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PJP20250504-03 *Eupithecia indigata* Ochreous Pug

Label details: record.date: 2025-05-04, site: Melton Mowbray Garden, VC: VC55, grid.ref: SK 7563 1803, recorder.name: Paul Palmer, comments: Cnephasia, determiner: Pete Leonard, method: Actinic Trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Geometridae, sub.family: Larentiinae, genus: Eupithecia, taxon: Eupithecia indigata, log.number: 70.171, Code: 1844, vernacular: Ochreous Pug, and gender: male.

Figure 17: PJP20250504-03 *Eupithecia indigata* Ochreous Pug specimen images.

Dissection

Very good visual match.

Figure 18: PJP20250504-03 *Eupithecia indigata* Ochreous Pug temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PJP20250512-01 *Aplocera plagiata* Treble-bar

Label details: record.date: 2025-05-10, site: Melton Mowbray Garden, VC: VC55, grid.ref: SK 7565 1803, recorder.name: Paul Palmer, comments: Treble Bar, determiner: Paul Palmer, method: Actinic Trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Geometridae, sub.family: Larentiinae, genus: Aplocera, taxon: Aplocera plagiata, log.number: 70.192, Code: 1867, vernacular: Treble-bar, and gender: female.

Figure 19: PJP20250512-01 *Aplocera plagiata* Treble-bar specimen images.

Dissection

Good visual match. Note signum shape.

Figure 20: PJP20250512-01 *Aplocera plagiata* Treble-bar temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250501-01 *No ID*

Label details: record.date: 2025-05-01, site: Harby garden, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 74421 30941, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: tortrix sp, determiner: Pete Leonard, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Tortricidae, taxon: No ID, and gender: female.

Figure 21: PML20250501-01 *No ID* specimen images.

Dissection

Identification not possible from this dissection, although several factors suggest it could well be *Epinotia immundana*: a very similar specimen was collected and identified as such on the same night in the same trap, the flight season fits very few other species, the external appearance of the adult, although very worn, would fit this species and what is observable in the dissection would fit this species, but too much is missing to be certain.

Figure 22: PML20250501-01 *No ID* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250501-02 *Epinotia immundana* Birch Tortrix

Label details: record.date: 2025-05-01, site: Harby garden, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 74421 30941, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: tortrix sp, determiner: Pete Leonard, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Tortricidae, sub.family: Olethreutinae, genus: *Epinotia*, taxon: *Epinotia immundana*, log.number: 49.240, Code: 1136, vernacular: Birch Tortrix, and gender: female.

Figure 23: PML20250501-02 *Epinotia immundana* Birch Tortrix specimen images.

Dissection

A good visual match.

Figure 24: PML20250501-02 *Epinotia immundana* Birch Tortrix temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250610-01 *No ID*

Label details: record.date: 2025-06-10, site: Harby garden, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 74421 30941, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: Cnephasia sp., determiner: Pete Leonard, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Tortricidae, sub.family: tortriciinae, genus: Cnephasia, taxon: No ID, log.number: , Code: , and gender: female.

Figure 25: PML20250610-01 *No ID* specimen images.

Dissection

Packed full of hard substance presumed to be eggs.

Specimen PML20250613-01 *Coleophora* sp.

Label details: record.date: 2025-06-13, site: Owsten Wood, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 79685 06681, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: *Coleophora* sp., determiner: Pete Leonard, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Coleophoridae, genus: *Coleophora*, and taxon: *Coleophora* sp..

Figure 26: PML20250613-01 *Coleophora* sp. specimen images.

Dissection

The dissection is not sufficient to get beyond genus so no ID possible.

Figure 27: PML20250613-01 *Coleophora* sp. temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250613-02 *Nemapogon cloacella* Cork Moth

Label details: record.date: 2025-06-13, site: Owsten Wood, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 79685 06681, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: *Nemapogon* agg., determiner: Pete Leonard, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Tineidae, sub.family: Nemapogoninae, genus: *Nemapogon*, taxon: *Nemapogon cloacella*, log.number: 12.016, Code: 216, vernacular: Cork Moth, and gender: male.

Figure 28: PML20250613-02 *Nemapogon cloacella* Cork Moth specimen images.

Dissection

Very good visual match.

Figure 29: PML20250613-02 *Nemapogon cloacella* Cork Moth temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250613-03 *Ancylis diminutana*

Label details: record.date: 2025-06-13, site: Owsten Wood, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 79685 06681, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: *Ancylis diminutana*?, determiner: Pete Leonard, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Tortricidae, sub.family: Olethreutinae, genus: *Ancylis*, taxon: *Ancylis diminutana*, log.number: 49.209, Code: 1119a, and gender: female.

Figure 30: PML20250613-03 *Ancylis diminutana* specimen images.

Dissection

Despite the rather worn imago and tricky dissection, both are a good visual match.

Figure 31: PML20250613-03 *Ancylis diminutana* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250613-04 *Notocelia rosaecolana*

Label details: record.date: 2025-06-13, site: Owsten Wood, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 79685 06681, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: *Notocelia rosaecolana*/trimaculana agg., determiner: Pete Leonard, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Tortricidae, sub.family: Olethreutinae, genus: *Notocelia*, taxon: *Notocelia rosaecolana*, log.number: 49.297, Code: 1177, and gender: male.

Figure 32: PML20250613-04 *Notocelia rosaecolana* specimen images.

Dissection

Good visual match.

Figure 33: PML20250613-04 *Notocelia rosaecolana* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250613-05 *Notocelia rosaecolana*

Label details: record.date: 2025-06-13, site: Owsten Wood, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 79685 06681, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: *Notocelia rosaecolana*/trimaculana agg., determiner: Pete Leonard, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Tortricidae, sub.family: Olethreutinae, genus: *Notocelia*, taxon: *Notocelia rosaecolana*, log.number: 49.297, Code: 1177, and gender: male.

Figure 34: PML20250613-05 *Notocelia rosaecolana* specimen images.

Dissection

Good visual match.

Figure 35: PML20250613-05 *Notocelia rosaecolana* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250616-01 *Acleris ferrugana*

Label details: record.date: 2025-06-16, site: Harby garden, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 74421 30941, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: *Acleris ferrugana*/notana agg., determiner: Pete Leonard, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Tortricidae, sub.family: Tortricinae, genus: *Acleris*, taxon: *Acleris ferrugana*, log.number: 49.083, Code: 1044, and gender: male.

Figure 36: PML20250616-01 *Acleris ferrugana* specimen images.

Dissection

Good visual match.

Figure 37: PML20250616-01 *Acleris ferrugana* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250616-02 *Anania coronata*

Label details: record.date: 2025-06-16, site: Harby garden, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 74421 30941, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: *Anania coronata* - aberrant individual?, determiner: Pete Leonard, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Crambidae, sub.family: Pyraustinae, genus: *Anania*, taxon: *Anania coronata*, log.number: 63.018, Code: 1378, and gender: male.

Figure 38: PML20250616-02 *Anania coronata* specimen images.

Dissection

Good visual match, confirming that the external appearance was just aberration.

Figure 39: PML20250616-02 *Anania coronata* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250618-01 *Coleophora flavipennella*

Label details: record.date: 2025-06-18, site: Harby garden, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 74421 30941, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: Coleophora sp., determiner: Pete Leonard, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Coleophoridae, sub.family: , genus: Coleophora, taxon: Coleophora flavipennella, log.number: 37.007, Code: 492, and gender: female.

Figure 40: PML20250618-01 *Coleophora flavipennella* specimen images.

Dissection

Very good visual match.

Figure 41: PML20250618-01 *Coleophora flavipennella* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250620-01 *Dichrorampha alpinana*

Label details: record.date: 2025-06-20, site: Valley View Farm, Saddington, VC: 55, grid.ref: SP 652 904, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: *Dichrorampha alpinana* agg., determiner: Pete Leonard, method: Actinic light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Tortricidae, sub.family: Olethreutinae, genus: *Dichrorampha*, taxon: *Dichrorampha alpinana*, log.number: 49.320, Code: 1274, and gender: female.

Figure 42: PML20250620-01 *Dichrorampha alpinana* specimen images.

Dissection

Good visual match.

Figure 43: PML20250620-01 *Dichrorampha alpinana* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250623-01 *Eupithecia dodoneata* Oak-tree Pug

Label details: record.date: 2025-06-23, site: Harby garden, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 74421 30941, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: Oak-tree Pug?, determiner: Pete Leonard, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Geometridae, sub.family: Larentiinae, genus: *Eupithecia*, taxon: *Eupithecia dodoneata*, log.number: 70.157, Code: 1853, vernacular: Oak-tree Pug, and gender: male.

Figure 44: PML20250623-01 *Eupithecia dodoneata* Oak-tree Pug specimen images.

Dissection

Very good visual match.

Figure 45: PML20250623-01 *Eupithecia dodoneata* Oak-tree Pug temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250624-01 *Blastobasis vittata*

Label details: record.date: 2025-06-24, site: Harby garden, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 74421 30941, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: Blastobasis vittata?, determiner: Pete Leonard, Andy Mitchell, Derek Lee, Peter Hall, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Blastobasidae, genus: Blastobasis, taxon: Blastobasis vittata, log.number: 41.004, Code: 873a, and gender: male.

Figure 46: PML20250624-01 *Blastobasis vittata* specimen images.

Dissection

Difficult to differentiate from *adustella*, but confirmation from Andy Mitchell, Derek Lee and Peter Hall. Gnathos tip relatively broad, valves narrow and the 'pillow' of setae all indicate this species. Also of note is that the imago is surprisingly distinctive and unlike *adustella*, despite being seemingly brown and featureless at first glance. This is a variable species, but on the three Harby individuals, the ground colour is warm brown and there are several black dots. The overall shape is slightly shorter and broader.

Figure 47: PML20250624-01 *Blastobasis vittata* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250625-01 *Scoparia ambigualis*

Label details: record.date: 2025-06-25, site: Harby garden, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 74421 30941, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: *Scoparia/Eudonia* sp., determiner: Pete Leonard, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Crambidae, sub.family: Scopariinae, genus: *Scoparia*, taxon: *Scoparia ambigualis*, log.number: 63.064, Code: 1334, and gender: female.

Figure 48: PML20250625-01 *Scoparia ambigualis* specimen images.

Dissection

Good visual match.

Figure 49: PML20250625-01 *Scoparia ambigualis* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250630-01 *Cnephasia* sp.

Label details: record.date: 2025-06-30, site: Harby garden, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 74421 30941, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: *Cnephasia* sp., determiner: Pete Leonard, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Tortricidae, sub.family: Tortricinae, genus: *Cnephasia*, taxon: *Cnephasia* sp., and gender: female.

Figure 50: PML20250630-01 *Cnephasia* sp. specimen images.

Dissection

The identification of females of the genus is very difficult and the dissection also makes it hard to see the relevant parts clearly. It is probably *asseclana*, though it is not possible to completely rule out *stephensiana*.

Figure 51: PML20250630-01 *Cnephasia* sp. temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250710-01 *Epinotia solandriana*

Label details: record.date: 2025-07-10, site: Owsten Wood, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 79685 06681, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: *Epinotia solandriana/sordidana*, determiner: Pete Leonard, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Tortricidae, sub.family: Olethreutinae, genus: *Epinotia*, taxon: *Epinotia solandriana*, log.number: 49.233, Code: 1156, and gender: male.

Figure 52: PML20250710-01 *Epinotia solandriana* specimen images.

Dissection

Good visual match.

Figure 53: PML20250710-01 *Epinotia solandriana* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250710-02 *Anacamptis blattariella* Birch Roller

Label details: record.date: 2025-07-10, site: Owsten Wood, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 79685 06681, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: *Anacamptis* sp., determiner: Guy Meredith, Peter Hall, Pete Leonard, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Gelechiidae, sub.family: Anacamptinae, genus: *Anacamptis*, taxon: *Anacamptis blattariella*, log.number: 35.012, Code: 854, vernacular: Birch Roller, and gender: male.

Figure 54: PML20250710-02 *Anacamptis blattariella* Birch Roller specimen images.

Dissection

The blunt shape of the uncus, broad and quite flat across the top, apart from the ridges which aren't parallel (unlike in *populella*) help to determine this species.

Figure 55: PML20250710-02 *Anacampsis blattariella* Birch Roller temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250710-03 *Agonopterix heracliana*

Label details: record.date: 2025-07-10, site: GWCT, Loddington LT1, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 79091 02595, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: *Agonopterix heracliana/ciliella*, determiner: Pete Leonard, Peter Hall, method: UV LED light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Depressariidae, sub.family: Depressariinae, genus: *Agonopterix*, taxon: *Agonopterix heracliana*, log.number: 32.018, Code: 688, and gender: male.

Figure 56: PML20250710-03 *Agonopterix heracliana* specimen images.

Dissection

A very interesting specimen. Despite showing 5 bands in the cilia, the dissection, and in particular the shape of the cullier, indicates that this is *A. heracliana* and not *A. ciliella*, confirming that counting the bands in the cilia is not a reliable method of separating this pair.

A few images were taken using a polarising microscope to explore the potential of this technique for emphasising heavily sclerotised structures. This may help to clarify the form of diagnostic processes in species such as *A. heracliana* and *A. ciliella*. (See Palmer (2026)).

Figure 57: PML20250710-03 *Agonopterix heracliana* temporary slide in aqueous mountant. Images taken with a polarising microscope are included for comparison.

Specimen PML20250711-01 *Endothenia marginana*

Label details: record.date: 2025-07-11, site: Harby garden, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 74421 30941, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: *Endothenia* sp., determiner: Pete Leonard, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Tortricidae, sub.family: Olethreutinae, genus: *Endothenia*, taxon: *Endothenia marginana*, log.number: 49.188, Code: 1099, and gender: male.

Figure 58: PML20250711-01 *Endothenia marginana* specimen images.

Dissection

A tricky dissection, but enough is visible to secure the identification of *marginana*, notably the uncus shape.

Figure 59: PML20250711-01 *Endothenia marginana* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250712-01 *Oegoconia quadripuncta*

Label details: record.date: 2025-07-12, site: Harby garden, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 74421 30941, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: *Oegoconia quadripuncta* agg., determiner: Pete Leonard, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Autostichidae, sub.family: Symmocinae, genus: *Oegoconia*, taxon: *Oegoconia quadripuncta*, log.number: 27.001, Code: 870, and gender: male.

Figure 60: PML20250712-01 *Oegoconia quadripuncta* specimen images.

Dissection

Not an ideal preparation, but a good visual match nevertheless.

Figure 61: PML20250712-01 *Oegoconia quadripuncta* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250713-01 *Blastobasis vittata*

Label details: record.date: 2025-07-13, site: Harby garden, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 74421 30941, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: *Blastobasis vittata*?, determiner: Pete Leonard, Andy Mitchell, Derek Lee, Peter Hall, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Blastobasidae, genus: *Blastobasis*, taxon: *Blastobasis vittata*, log.number: 41.004, Code: 873a, and gender: male.

Figure 62: PML20250713-01 *Blastobasis vittata* specimen images.

Dissection

Comments as for PML20250624-01

Figure 63: PML20250713-01 *Blastobasis vittata* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250717-01 *Elachista consortella*

Label details: record.date: 2025-07-17, site: Harby garden, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 74421 30941, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: Elachista sp. - prob freyerella/stabilella, determiner: Pete Leonard, Jim Hodgkinson, Paul Palmer, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Elachistidae, sub.family: , genus: Elachista, taxon: Elachista consortella, log.number: 38.048, Code: 632, and gender: female.

Figure 64: PML20250717-01 *Elachista consortella* specimen images.

Dissection

A good visual match, both externally and internally.

Figure 65: PML20250717-01 *Elachista consortella* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20250824-01 *No ID*

Label details: record.date: 2025-08-24, site: GWCT, Loddington LT3, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 79194 02642, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: Elachista sp., determiner: , method: Actinic light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Elachistidae, genus: Elachista, and taxon: No ID.

Figure 66: PML20250824-01 *No ID* specimen images.

Dissection

Specimen lost, no ID.

Specimen PML20250919-01 *Acleris emargana*

Label details: record.date: 2025-09-19, site: Harby garden, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 74421 30941, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: Acleris emargana/effractana agg., no photo, determiner: Peter Hall, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Tortricidae, sub.family: Tortricinae, genus: Acleris, taxon: Acleris emargana, log.number: 49.071, Code: 1062, and gender: female.

Figure 67: PML20250919-01 *Acleris emargana* specimen images.

Dissection

Peter Hall comments: 'the ductus bursa looks pretty straight which would make it emargana.'

Figure 68: PML20250919-01 *Acleris emargana* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

Specimen PML20251017-01 *Blastobasis vittata*

Label details: record.date: 2025-10-17, site: Harby garden, VC: 55, grid.ref: SK 74421 30941, recorder.name: Pete Leonard, comments: *Blastobasis vittata*?, determiner: Pete Leonard, Andy Mitchell, Derek Lee, Peter Hall, method: MV light trap, stage: Adult, quantity: 1, order: Lepidoptera, family: Blastobasidae, genus: *Blastobasis*, taxon: *Blastobasis vittata*, log.number: 41.004, Code: 873a, and gender: male.

Figure 69: PML20251017-01 *Blastobasis vittata* specimen images.

Dissection

Comments as for PML20250624-01

Figure 70: PML20251017-01 *Blastobasis vittata* temporary slide in aqueous mountant.

References

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- Schön, Walter. 2021. "Lepiforum." <http://lepiforum.org/>.